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Identifying a person using dynamic biometric authentication methods

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Abstract: Biometric methods are aimed at identifying a person based on their unique characteristics. The article considers keyboard handwriting as a dynamic biometric characteristic. The features necessary for identification are analyzed and selected. The algorithm for generating a keystroke dynamics pattern is based on recording time parameters. Classical statistical approaches to identifying users based on keystroke dynamics are considered. To solve the identification problem, it is proposed to use a client-server application, its characteristics are given, tests are conducted, and the results are analyzed.

Keywords: FAR, FRR, dynamic biometric characteristics, identification, biometrics, data protection, keystroke dynamics, information security, database

INTRODUCTION

Currently, significant attention is being devoted to the enhancement, development, and implementation of methods and algorithms for identity recognition based on biometric technologies. With the development and expansion of the scope of application of computer technologies, the seriousness of the problem of ensuring security in computing systems and controlling access in distributed information systems is increasing for a number of objective reasons [1].

In the field of information security, biometrics is understood as a field of knowledge that describes the method of identifying and verifying a person's identity based on their physiological and behavioral characteristics. While in the 1990s, biometric systems were mainly used to protect military facilities and especially sensitive commercial information, now airports, large shopping malls, and many company offices are equipped with biometric systems for use.

The increasing demand has stimulated research in this area, leading to the emergence of new technologies and devices.

Protecting data transmission requires mutual authentication of entities, that is, confirmation of the authenticity of entities connected through communication channels. From a security point of view, each of the above allows solving its own problems.

One of the currently promising approaches is to recognize text typed on the keyboard by analyzing the dynamic biometric characteristics of a person. This method is based on analyzing the following user characteristics [8]:

- Text input speed;
- Key press duration [2];
- time intervals between key presses;

- Number of errors during input (delete button click rate);
- Frequency of use of function keys and combinations relative to one type of input device;
- The degree of arrhythmia during the dialing process and other factors.

GENERAL DESCRIPTIONS OF BIOMETRIC AUTHENTICATION METHODS.

Biometric methods provide identification of a person based on their individual characteristics. The main advantage of these methods is that such characteristics cannot be stolen or transferred to another person.

Biometric methods are divided into physiological, behavioral, and combined methods. Their detailed classification is presented in Figure 1.

While behavioral traits are harder to identify with high accuracy, they are also harder to fake.

Modern biometric authentication is based on two methods [15]:

1) Static method. This is an authentication method that is based on identifying physical characteristics that do not change throughout a person's life. These include fingerprints, iris characteristics, retinal patterns, thermograms, facial geometry, hand geometry, and even parts of the genetic code.

2) Dynamic method. This is an authentication method based on analyzing behavioral characteristics that a user exhibits during their daily activities (e.g., signing, typing, making sounds, etc.).

Biometric authentication does not verify the user with absolute accuracy. Since some applications of strong cryptographic systems, such as authentication systems based on post-quantum transformation, are currently at the theoretical justification and prototype development stage [5], biometric characteristics of users play an important role in the identity verification process. In such cases, there is a possibility of type I (access denied) and type II (invalid access) errors occurring [7].

Figure 1 - Classification of biometric methods

The effectiveness of biometric authentication systems is usually assessed by two main characteristics:

- False Rejection (Type I Error – FRR, False Rejection Rate) refers to the probability with which the system fails to recognize a registered user.
- False Access (Type II Error – FAR, False Access Rate) refers to the probability of an unauthorized user being erroneously granted access to the system.

The process of obtaining an individual's evaluation data involves the one-time, periodic, or continuous collection of information about their actions while entering a control word or dataset characteristic of their regular activities.

The main place in the biometric systems market has always belonged to static methods, while dynamic authentication and combined information protection systems occupy only 20% of the market [17].

It should be noted that classical biometric authentication using static methods has a number of problems [13]:

Identify the user only at a certain stage of interaction: login, transaction confirmation, etc.;

- Approaches are based on the analysis of the user's personal data;
- Requires the installation of special technical devices;
- Each additional identification process reduces the success rate of the transaction by 15-20%;

- Based on external (visible) physiological characteristics.

Dynamic biometric authentication methods have the following advantages over static methods:

- Continuous monitoring to detect unauthorized access throughout the entire operation;
- Does not require changing user behavior (hidden identification method);
- Works on all platforms and devices without additional equipment.

It is known that in recent years the development of dynamic protection methods shows a clear trend [12]. A comparison of existing methods is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of the effectiveness of using biometric authentication methods

Biometric authentication method	Price	User comfort	Falsification	FAR (False Acceptance Rate)	FRR (False Rejection Rate)
2D Face Recognition	Medium	Medium	Possible	0,1%	2,5 %
3D Face Recognition	High	Medium, Low medium	Problematic	0,0005%	0,1 %
Fingerprint	Low	Medium	Possible	0,001%	0,6 %
Iris	High	High	Impossible	0,00001%	0,016 %
Retina of the eye	High	Low	Impossible	0,0001%	0,4 %
Palm veins pattern	Medium	Medium	Impossible	0,0008%	0,01 %
Voice	Low	Medium	Possible	0,75%	0,75 %
Keystroke dynamics	Low	High	Possible	0.01%	0,01 %

Based on the above data, it can be said that the use of dynamic biometric authentication methods, especially the keyboard handwriting method, meets the requirements. It should be noted that three main requirements for authentication must be met [14]:

- Knowledge of information known to the user, such as a password or passphrase;
- Possession of a device specific to the user, such as a computer;
- Biometric data that is specific to the user and allows for the precise identification of the individual.

The role of statistical algorithms in dynamic authentication and identification methods.

Comprehensive research on biometric methods conducted by the National Bureau of Standards has estimated the likelihood of users acquiring keyboard operation skills at 98%, highlighting the successful practical implementation of such systems [16].

Keyboard typing analysis has its own advantages and disadvantages [6], just like other biometric methods [1].

The advantages include the following:

- Biometric identification relies solely on a person’s physical characteristics and does not require any files or passwords.
- The inherent nature of human characteristics makes them extremely difficult to forge.
- Unlike paper-based identifiers (such as passports, driver’s licenses, insurance cards, or tax identification numbers), passwords, or personal identification numbers, biometrics cannot be forgotten or lost; they can always be easily “presented”.

There are a number of complexities in keyboard input analysis [9]:

- Changes in keyboard typing parameters depending on the psychophysical state of the user;
- Changes in keyboard typing parameters based on the keyboard used by the user. According to a scientific study [11], testing a user's typing on different keyboards resulted in a 0.5% difference in the probability of authentication.
- The need to collect a large amount of statistical data for each keystroke analysis, and the lack of databases with KD samples.

Let us focus on the most widely studied approach based on probabilistic-static methods. We compare statistical algorithms with respect to evaluation criteria specific to some functional properties [16] (see Table 2).

Table 2. Authentication and identification using statistical algorithms

Parameters	Test type	Recognition method	FAR	FRR	ERR	Users	Samples
Dwell Time	Statistical	Static	0,47	1,32	2,2	64	310
	Statistical	Dynamic	-	-	-	25	1620
	Hypothesis	Static	1,4	1,4	1,41	100	5000
	Manhattan distance	Static	-	-	9,6	51	20400
	Angle b/w latencies	Static	3,6	4,7	-	15	-
Flight Time	Statistical	Static	0	2,3	-	44	220
	Distance measure (Hamming measure)	Dynamic	8,33	2,6	-	31	-
	Relative, Abs. Distance	Static, Dynamic	0,00 5	5	0,5	205	765
	Degree of disorder	Static	0	0,55	-	18	810
Dwell Time, Flight Time	Statistical	Dynamic	9	5	-	21	-

Based on the results obtained, authentication based on keyboard keystroke analysis can be considered effective. It should also be noted that there is currently no keyboard keystroke analysis application for computer devices, which confirms the importance of further research into dynamic biometric authentication methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Introducing dynamic biometric authentication methods based on statistical algorithms. The software being developed is designed to continuously collect information about keyboard keystrokes in Russian/English and identify authorized or unauthorized user actions.

The system is implemented based on client-server architecture. On the client side, there is a program that allows you to read biometric data - keystrokes. The test sample contains the entered password and dynamic properties, as well as the name of the authentication profile. In other words, in the first step, the user registers with the program and thereby creates a profile name. In the second stage, a test pattern is created by entering a passphrase throughout the entire interaction with the device's keyboard, and the time spent holding down the keys is read. The data is sent to the server and, through mathematical calculations, a standard pattern of user keystroke dynamics is formed.

On the server side, there is a database that stores standard data for authentication, and the test samples and standards comparison algorithms also run on the server. As a result, the server returns the final comparison result to the client.

To protect against attacks by unidentified individuals, a secure communication channel is established between the server and the client [10]. The main stages of the application are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Steps to use the software

The feature collection stage involves the process of obtaining the values of the parameters described above.

The keyboard template formation stage involves analyzing the values of the obtained parameters, in particular the keystroke durations, and forming a reference template for future comparison based on the values obtained when attempting to log in to the system. The keyboard profile database update phase updates the standards stored in the database. User authentication consists of the processes of verifying the user's identity, granting or denying access.

Currently, there are 2 methods for implementing user authentication based on keyboard dynamics [8]:

1. using a pre-known passphrase;
2. continuously monitoring the user's keyboard activity throughout the entire time the device is being used.

The password method can be used during the authorization stage, but it is more complicated to use, as using this method requires a significant reduction in user experience.

The essence of continuous monitoring is that it can be used both during authentication and after it has been completed:

- Monitoring all user keyboard activity. This requires a large number of resources for the decision-making device, as it requires storing timestamps of all characters entered by the user in a standard database;
- The approach based on frequent bigrams. This requires fewer resources, as only the most frequent letter pairs are used [2].

As part of our scientific research, we have developed a passphrase detection application. This application performs 3 stages of keystroke dynamics detection:

- 1) training;
- 2) threshold formation;
- 3) recognition.

During the training phase, the user enters the password 20 times and sends the data to the server [12]. The received values are processed on the server and a keyboard handwriting standard is formed. The standard is formed based on the principle of calculating the average value of a parameter such as key hold time.

During the threshold generation stage, the user enters the passphrase 5 times and sends the data to the server. At this stage, the Hamming metric is formed on the server [10], in other words, the value of the number of permissible deviations between the time parameters a_1 and the standard a_2 is generated:

$$H = a_1 \oplus a_2. \quad (1)$$

To identify a user by keyboard input, two-dimensional vector values are observed [12]:

$$P = (t_r, t_i), \quad (2)$$

where t_r is the holding time; t_i is the pause duration.

During the authentication phase, after entering the password, the user sees a positive or negative response from the server on the screen. This response indicates whether the user is an “authenticated user” or an “unauthenticated user”.

The application was tested with several users. The users were two students of different genders, aged 18-23. During the testing process, each user trained the system and formed a standard keystroke dynamic (Table 3).

Table 3. Testing the “keystroke_v1” application

Meaning of Hamming measure	The number of repetitions of entering the password during the training phase	The number of characters sent to the server to train the system	Number of recognition iterations	The first type of error rate (FRR)	The second type of error rate (FAR)
User1:46,6	20	120	45	0,44	0
User2:46,6				0,53	0,04
User1:50	40	240	45	0,73	0,044
User2:26,66				0,08	0,77
User1:52,5	60	360	45	0,6	0,42
User2:46,6				0,28	0,64

The following facts were identified during the analysis of Table 3:

- high percentage of type I errors in the first test for the first and second users (44% and 53%, respectively);
- high percentage of type I errors in the second test for the first user (73%), high percentage of type II errors for the second user (77%);
- high percentage of type I errors in the third test for the first user (60%), for the second user – 28%, high percentage of type II errors for the first user – 42%, for the second user – 64%.

The reasons for obtaining these results may be the following facts:

- users experienced discomfort;
- individual psychophysiological state at the time of testing;
- monotonous repetition of the same type of movements in a short period of time.

At this stage of development, the program creates a reference template based on a single parameter, the time the keys are held down, and a passphrase known to both the legitimate user and the attacker. Table 4 presents the results obtained.

Table 4. Testing the "keystroke_v1" application

User	Time parameter value for "r" character, ms (milliseconds)	Time parameter value for "f" character, ms (milliseconds)	Time parameter value for "n" character, ms (milliseconds)	Time parameter value for "e" character, ms (milliseconds)	Time parameter value for "c" character, ms (milliseconds)	The number of repetitions of entering the password during the training phase
User1	80,5	75	97	79	60	20
User2	89	94,5	96,4	87,5	86,5	
User1	86	96	84	87,5	88,5	40
User2	102	101	88,5	86	78	
User1	85	83,5	91,5	92	69,5	60
User2	95	80,5	81,5	90,5	103,5	

Based on the results presented in Table 4, the following conclusions were drawn:

- There was no consistent value for any of the keyboard style template parameters among users, so it can be concluded that each person has a unique typing style;
- During the first test of the system, the smallest difference was observed when pressing and holding the "n" key (0.6 ms), and the largest difference was observed when pressing and holding the "f" key (19.5 ms);
- For the second test of the system, the smallest difference was observed when pressing and holding the "e" key (1.5 ms), and the largest difference was observed when pressing and holding the "r" key (16 ms);
- For the third test of the system, the smallest difference was observed when pressing and holding the "e" key (1.5 ms), and the largest difference was observed when pressing and holding the "c" key (34 ms).

CONCLUSION

According to the test results, it can be concluded that a large percentage of errors of the first and second types are due to insufficient data received on the server to form the keystroke dynamics standard. A single parameter (key hold time) is not enough to model keystroke dynamics. It is important to note that the test was conducted continuously for three experiments. Users entered a certain phrase in a monotonous manner for a while, which was inconvenient for the user. It follows that further tests should be conducted over a long period of time (at least

24 hours) to observe the trend of changes in keystroke dynamics of different people over the same period of time.

It should also be noted that monotonous input of a fixed phrase leads to distortion of the results, which leads to the conclusion that it is more appropriate to conduct tests on free text input.

The problem of assessing the stability and individuality of biometric characteristics remains. Nevertheless, the proposed approach to recognizing a user's biometric image based on keystroke dynamics allows us to reliably identify individuals. Also, additional research is needed in this area, aimed at increasing the reliability and accuracy of the results, modernizing the graphical interface, optimizing the speed of operation, etc.

The research results revealed the following advantages of using dynamic methods of biometric user authentication:

- 1) There is no need to purchase additional equipment [2];
- 2) No additional skills or actions are required from the user;
- 3) If covert authentication is provided, the user may not be aware that additional verification has been enabled and, therefore, cannot notify the intruder about it [15] (if the continuous monitoring method is applied).

The efficiency of user recognition based on dynamic biometric authentication methods reaches 92.14%, which allows us to speak about the high potential of using this method in the development of computer access systems.

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